

Isolation and Identification of Some Microbial Pathogens Associated Body Surfaces of Cockroaches in Residential Areas Within Sokoto State Metropolis

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ABSTRACT:

Cockroach (*Periplaneta americana*) harbour and disseminate the bacterial pathogens to the metropolis. They play important role in the transmission of different diseases either mechanically, occasionally and biologically. The presence of these cockroaches in the houses especially kitchens is an indicator of poor food hygiene. Cockroaches may spread a range of diseases and are a health hazard. They carry bacteria and fungi on their bodies from rubbish bins, sewers, drains and garbage areas and then transmit it to individuals by visiting their kitchens. The study was attempted to isolate and identify the pathogenic bacteria and fungi from the household room, toilet and kitchen areas of different houses in the metropolis. Cockroaches were collected by using sticky traps and direct collection. Pathogenic bacteria and fungi were isolated from the external surfaces of 100% of the American cockroaches examined. The following bacteria were identified *Escherichia*, *Staphylococcus*, *Enterobacter*, *Bacillus*, *Aeromonas* *Vibrio* *Pleisiomonas* and *Salmonella* Species. While fungal isolates recovered include *Aspergillus* specie, *Mucor* specie, *Penicillium* specie, *Fusarium* specie and *Rhizopus* specie. Total viable count and microbial loads of the isolates from the three sites revealed that the isolates obtained from toilet areas were high as compared to those from kitchen and rooms areas. This indicated that *Periplaneta americana* is a possible reservoir of several pathogens via their bodies.

Keyword: Microbial, Fungi, Bacteria, *Periplaneta americana*, Body surface and Homes.

INTRODUCTION

Microbial load is the amount or number of organisms that are found in both animate and inanimate objects. The insect-vectors on the other hand are the insect that carry some microorganisms which are involved in vector-borne diseases, which vary greatly, ranging from fungi, bacteria, viruses to tiny nematode worms [1]. Cockroaches are among the most common pests in many homes and other buildings. At night they search for food in kitchens, food storage places, rubbish bins, drains and sewers. They are pests because of their filthy habits and bad smell. Some people may become allergic to cockroaches after frequent exposure. Cockroaches can sometimes play a role as carriers of intestinal diseases, such as diarrhoea, dysentery, typhoid fever and cholera [2].

The fact that cockroaches carry microbial organisms has been reported for many years, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Citrus* and *Bacillus of the subtilis* type were isolated from cockroaches in hospital wards and residential areas [3]. A study in central Tehran, Iran reported that at least 25 different species of medically important bacteria and fungi were identified, the most frequent being *Klebsiella species*, from *Periplaneta americana* collected from public hospitals and a residential house. Cockroaches from hospitals were more likely to be contaminated with medically important bacteria and fungi. A study by Cotton *et al.* from South Africa compared pathogenic strains from cockroaches and those which colonize infants and found no difference [4]. Cockroaches were trapped from food dispensing areas (kitchens). Consisting of *Periplaneta americana* (67.3%), *Blattella germanica* (26%), *P. brunnea* (4.8%), and *Supella longipalpa* (1.9%). Bacteria were isolated from all cockroaches except some *P. brunnea*. Many bacterial and fungal species were identified, including the pathogenic and potentially pathogenic species *Shigella boydii*, *S. dysenteriae*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Klebsiella oxytoca*, *K. ozaena* and *Serratia marcescens* *Aspergillus* specie, *Mucor* specie, *Penicillium* specie, *Fusarium* specie, *Candida* specie and *Rhizopus* [5].

Furthermore, a comparative analysis of pathogenic organisms in cockroaches from different socio-economic community settings in Edo State, Nigeria showed that organisms such as *Bacillus spp.*, *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *proteus vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Citrobacter freundii* and *Salmonella spp* can be harbored on the body surface and alimentary tract of cockroaches [6].

The main objective of this study was to isolate and identified pathogenic microorganisms on the external body parts of American cockroach (*Periplaneta americana*) from kitchens, toilet and house rooms collected from different homes of Sokoto State metropolis, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This study on isolation and identification of pathogenic microorganisms (bacteria) on the external body parts of American cockroach (*Periplaneta americana*) from kitchens, toilet and house in Sokoto metropolis was carried out in Sokoto metropolis of the Sokoto state. The State geographically lies along longitude 11⁰ 30¹ to 13⁰ 50¹ East and latitudes 4⁰ to 6¹ North and covers a total land mass of 26,648.48 square kilometres. Sokoto State shares boundary with Kebbi State to the south, Zamfara State to the east and the Republic of Niger to the north. The State has an estimated population of about 4,742,459 people as of 2015 with 95.9 persons per square kilometre, and 3% growth rate annually based on 2006 population census [7]. Occupation of city inhabitants includes farming, trading, commerce, with a reasonable proportion of the population working in private and public sectors [8, 9].

Samples Analysis

One hundred and fifty (150) samples were collected from toilet, room and kitchens of different houses within Sokoto metropolis. All these samples were used for the culturing of microorganisms. Sample analysis was done according to the

standard plate count procedures outlined by Oyeleke and Manga [10].

Serial dilution was carried out by pipetting 1ml from the stock bottle and transferring it to another universal bottle containing 9mls of distilled water. This bottle was marked 10¹. Similar procedures were carried out up to 10⁶. From the bottle with dilution of 10⁶, media inoculation was done.

Media Preparation

Nutrient agar and Mac Ckonkey agar were prepared according to the manufacturers procedures. Twenty three gram (23g) of the powder (Nutrient agar) was weighed using a balance and transferred into 1000ml distilled water contained in a conical flask. Heating was done to dissolve the powder completely. This was followed by autoclaving at 121°C for 15mins. This was dispersed into the Petridis and allowed to solidify. Fifty two gram (52g) of the dry powder (Mac Ckonkey agar) was weighed using a balance and transferred into 1000ml distilled water contained in a conical flask. Heating was done to dissolve the powder completely. This was dispersed into the petridishes and allowed to solidify.

Inoculation and Subculture

0.1ml of the diluents from 10⁶ tube for bacteria and 10³ for fungi was transferred to the petridishes using a pipette. A sterilized bent glass rod (in alcohol) was used to spread the inoculums over the surface of the petridishes. The set up was incubated at 37°C for 24hrs. Plates showing no growth were further incubated for 48hrs before discarding. The suspected

colonies after gram stained were subculture on another fresh nutrient agar plate for pure culture. Confirmed purified isolates (bacteria) were transferred to slants for further analysis mostly biochemical reactions.

Biochemical Reactions

The following reactions were carried out; catalase, coagulase, mannitol, reactions on Triple sugar Iron Agar, spore staining temperature treatment, urease, oxidase, citrate and MRVP. The procedures were according to the method described by Oyeleke and Manga [10].

Fungal Analysis

Fungal cultures were made with Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) impregnated with antibiotics and incubated for 5 days. The isolates were identified by staining with lacto-phenol cotton blue on glass slide in which a portion of the fungi were collected using sterile needle. The fungal isolates were identified on the basis of their colonial morphology on the SDA medium and type of hyphae after subcultures were made.

RESULTS

A total of one hundred and fifty (150) samples were obtained for this investigation, Fifty (50) samples were collected from each residential location. More than Eighty nine samples were positive, with toilet being 100% followed by kitchen with 90% and 78% in rooms. The total number of collected samples and positive samples were presented in table 1.

Table 1. Cockroaches analyzed from the sampling location

Sample location	No. of samples collected	Positive sample (%)
Toilet	50	50 (100)
Kitchen	50	45 (90)
Room	50	39 (78)
Total	150	134 (89.3)

Table 2. The microbial load of cockroaches in three housing locations (cfu/ml)

Sampling Location	Range of count	Means count
Toilet	2.0 x 10 ⁶ - 3.8 x 10 ⁶	2.68 x 10 ⁶
Kitchen	7.2 x 10 ⁴ - 9.6 x 10 ⁴	7.87 x 10 ⁴
Room	4.8 x 10 ⁴ - 5.4 x 10 ⁴	5.17 x 10 ⁴

Table 3: Frequency and percentage of bacteria isolated from the external body surfaces of cockroaches

Bacteria isolates	Toilet NO. (%)	Kitchen NO. (%)	Room NO. (%)	Total NO. (%)
<i>Bacillus</i> spp.	6 (21.4)	7 (26.9)	1 (6.3)	14 (20)
<i>Escherichia</i> spp.	4 (14.3)	4 (15.4)	3 (18.7)	11 (15.7)
<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.	3 (10.7)	2 (7.7)	4 (25)	9 (12.8)
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	6 (21.4)	4 (15.4)	2 (12.5)	12 (17.1)
<i>Enterobacter</i> spp.	2 (7.1)	3 (11.5)	1(6.3)	6 (8.6)
<i>Aeromonas</i> spp.	1 (3.6)	2 (7.7)	1(6.3)	4 (5.7)
<i>Vibrio</i> spp.	2 (7.1)	1 (3.8)	2 (12.5)	5 (7.1)
<i>Pleisiomonas</i> spp.	4 (14.3)	3 (11.5)	2 (12.5)	9 (12.8)
Total	28 (100)	26 (100)	16 (100)	70 (100)

Table 4: Frequency and percentage of fungi isolated from the external body surfaces of cockroaches

Bacteria isolates	Toilet NO. (%)	Kitchen NO. (%)	Room NO. (%)	Total NO. (%)
<i>Aspergillus</i> spp.	23 (59)	17 (53.1)	11 (47.8)	51 (54.3)
<i>Pennicillium</i> spp.	7 (18)	4 (12.5)	3 (13)	14 (14.9)
<i>Rhizophus</i> spp.	4 (10.3)	4 (12.5)	2 (8.7)	10 (10.6)
<i>Fusarium</i> spp.	2 (5.1)	2 (6.2)	6 (26)	10 (10.6)
<i>Mucur</i> spp.	3 (7.7)	5 (15.6)	1 (4.3)	9 (9.6)
Total	39 (100)	32 (100)	23 (100)	94 (100)

The Microbial load of the samples examine has been identified. The toilet areas have highest range of Microbial load with 2.68 x 10⁶ as mean of total colonies followed by kitchen with 7.87 x 10⁴ total mean. The range, mean counts and percentage Positive samples of each location is presented in table 2

Frequency and percentages of bacterial isolates identified from body surface of cockroaches shows that toilet areas are more contaminated with 28 bacterial isolates, the least in abundance is rooms areas with only 16 isolates. *Bacillus* species are common and more abundant with 20%, followed by isolates of

Salmonella and *Escherichia* species with 17.1% and 15.7 respectively, the least encountered organisms is *Aeromonas* specie with 5.7% only. The results are presented in table 3.

The fungi isolated from this investigation shows that toilet area are prone to fungi than the other location investigated, *Aspergillus* species have higher number of occurrence with 54.3%. the least encountered fungal isolates was *Mucur* specie with 9.6% only. The results are presented in table 4

DISCUSSION

Cultural and biochemical reactions have been carried out on different suspected isolates as gram positive rods, gram negative rods, and gram positive cocci. In all about 8 genera have been isolated as *S. aureus*, *S. saprophyticus*, *E. coli*, *Salmonella* Species, *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Vibrio cholerae*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Enterobacter agglomerans*, *Bacillus brevis* *B. sphaericus*, and *B. subtilis*

These findings agree with the results of Chaichanawongsaroj [11] in Thailand, which showed presence *Enterobacter* specie, *Klebsiella* specie, *Citrobacter* specie, *E. coli*, *Salmonella* specie, *Proteus* specie, *Serratia* specie, species on the *Periplaneta Americana* and *Blatta orientalis* collected from Hospital, Food-handling establishments and human dwellings [11, 12]. Similar bacteria have been isolated from *P. americana* and *B. germanica* in another study [6]. However, they are known as pathogenic (*Salmonella*, *Shigella*, *B. cereus*), opportunistic pathogens (*Pseudomonas*, *Klebsiella*, *Vibrio*) and food spoilage species (*Pseudomonas*, *Enterobacter*, *Escherichia*, *Erwinia*) they belong to cockroach transmitted bacteria [6, 15]. Bacterial species, such as *Klebsiella* spp., *E. coli*, *Staphylococcus* spp., *Enterobacter* spp., *Streptococcus* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., *Proteus* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *Neisseria* spp., *Shigella* spp., and *Salmonella* spp., have also been isolated from *P. Americana* and *Polyphaga aegyptica* cockroaches by other researchers from Khuzestan [13, 14, 16].

A total of 94 fungal organisms were isolated from the external body parts of cockroaches from the three areas covered by this study which was in agreement with [1]. The presence of these organisms in very large numbers was at variance with the report of [6]. Non isolation of *Rhizopus* spp in this study from cockroaches obtained from health facilities disagrees with the findings of [15]. High prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp 33.16% agrees with the work of [4]

Cockroaches are one of the most appalling sights, especially when they are in our home, kitchen nearby foods, and bathrooms. Any bug indoors will scare someone, but cockroaches are far worse than other household pests. Cockroaches carry many pathogens, they pick up from contaminated places such as: sewers, drains, garbage, landfills, bathrooms, and toilets. Many health risks come along with a cockroach infestation. These cockroaches are typical to causes many intestinal diseases and illnesses [17].

The discovery of such pathogens is not uncommon since the vectors are known to inhabit or visits such location as toilets and gutters, dustbin and shades where most of the human waste are discharged.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that cockroaches are insect-vectors responsible for insects borne diseases, because they carry a lot of pathogens (microorganisms) and help in transmission of these pathogens that in turn can cause disease to general populace. It is recommended that suitable steps must be taken to control the cockroaches and monitor the sensitivity pattern of the pathogens transmitted by the cockroaches.

REFERENCES

1. A A Yalli, Sambo S., Lawal H.M. and Tukur U. Study of Bacteria On the Body Surfaces of House Flies (*Musca Domestica*) In Some Homes Within Sokoto Metropolis. J. of Advancement in Medical and Life Sciences. (2017) V5I4. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1000685
2. M.K. Rust, D.A. Reiersen, K.H. Hansgen. Control of American cockroaches (Dictyoptera: Blattidae) in sewers. *Journal of medical entomology*, (1991), 28: 210–213.
3. R. Foteddar, Vector potential of house flies (*Musca domestica*) in the transmission of vibrio cholerae in India. *Acta. Trop.* 78 (2001) (1): 31–4.
4. M. Cotton, E. Wasserman, C. Pieper, Invasive disease due to extended spectrum beta-lactamase-producing *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in a neonatal unit: The possible role of cockroaches. *Journal of Hospital Infections.* (2000) 44 (1):13-17.
5. P. Oothuman, J. Jeffery, A.H. Azi, E. Abubakar, M. Jegathesan. Bacterial pathogens isolated from cockroaches trapped from pediatric wards in Peninsular Malaysia. *Journal of Medical Hygiene.* (1989) 83:133- 135.
6. I. Clement, OO. Philip, II. Mercy, I.E. Joy, I. Osesojie, Comparative analysis of pathogenic organisms in cockroaches from different community settings in Edo State, Nigeria. *Korean Journal of Parasitology.* (2014) 52(2):177-181.
7. National Population Commission (NPC, 2007). Population Census Data, Nigeria, Federal Republic of Nigeria Official Gazette, National and State Provisional Total Census, Printed and Published in Federal Government Printer, Lagos, 2007 No 21 vol.94
8. MOCIT, Guide to Sokoto states Economic Potentials. Commerce Dept, Ministry of Commerce, Industry and Tourism, Sokoto State. (2002). Pp 4 – 18.
9. S.B. Oyeleke, and B.S Manga, Essential of laboratory practicals in microbiology 1st ed. Tobest publishers S.W. 225 Hospital road Minna, Nigeria State (2008) pp. 28 - 58.
10. N. Chaichanawongsaroj, K. Vanichayatanarak, T. Pipatkullachat, M. Polrojpanya, S. Somkiatcharoen. Isolation of gram-negative bacteria from cockroaches trapped from urban environment. *Southeast Asian J Trop Med Public Health.* (2004) 35 (3): 681–684.
11. A. Salehzadeh, P. Tavacol, H Mahjub, Bacterial, fungal and parasitic contamination of cockroaches in public hospitals of Hamadan, Iran. *J Vect Borne Dis.* (2007) 44: 105–110.
12. B. Vazirianzadeh, M. Mehdinejad, R. Dehghani, Identification of bacteria which possible transmitted by *Polyphagaegyptica* (Blattodea: Blattidae) in the region of Ahvaz, SW Iran. *Jundishapur J Microbiol.* (2011) 2 (1): 36–40.
13. H. Kassiri, S. Kazemi, Cockroaches [*Periplaneta americana* (L.), Dictyoptera, Blattidae] as Carriers of Bacterial Pathogens, Khorramshahr County, Iran. *Jundishapur J Microbiol.* (2012) 5(1): 320–322
14. H.H. Pai, WC. Chen, CF Peng, Isolation of bacteria with antibiotic resistance from household cockroaches (*Periplaneta americana* and *Blattella germanica*). *Acta Trop.* (2005) 93 : 259–65
15. C.M. Gibson, MS. Hunter, Inherited Fungal and Bacterial Endosymbionts of a Parasitic Wasp and Its Cockroach Host *Microb Ecol.* (2009) 57: 542–549.
16. J. Mitchell, T. De-Medina, C. Yehuda, Epidemiological interpretation of antibiotic resistance studies: what are we missing? *Nature Rev Microbiol.* (2004) 2: 979–983.

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